

Organophilic Characteristics and Waterproofness of Clay-organic Complexes*

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The organophilic and water-repellent character of organo-clay derivatives, obtained from hydrogen clays, and their binary mixtures has been shown by the behaviour of the latter towards single polar and nonpolar liquids and pairs of immiscible or partially miscible liquids. The organophilic character of the clay minerals is more prominent, the higher their exchange capacity and the greater the amount of the organics absorbed by them. Nonpolar liquids and those of high dielectric constant are more efficient in solvating the organo-clay derivatives. The kaolin derivatives are the least organophilic and water-repellent. In presence of water and another immiscible liquid, the kaolin derivatives prefer the aqueous phase unless these are first wetted with an organo-liquid of highly polar and organophilic character. The other clay derivatives, e.g., those of montmorillonite, vermiculite, etc., choose the organic phase under similar conditions. The individual characteristics of the component clay derivatives in a mixture of them are retained when treated with a binary liquid system.

The variations of sedimentation volume and swelling of the organo-clay derivatives with varying concentrations of the components in a mixture of EtOH-CO₂ are interesting. One maximum is observed for montmorillonite derivatives and sometimes two, if the experimental conditions are slightly changed. Illite and Illitic soil clay derivatives show three maxima. Mica and kaolin derivatives show little change, if at all. The results have been explained by taking into account the relevant factors involved.

The X-ray studies strongly suggest the formation of three layers of the organic molecules between the basal plane surfaces of montmorillonite. For finer particles the number of layers may be 6 or even greater. The X-ray and adsorption data of vermiculite also suggest the formation of multilayers of organic molecules in the basal planes.

The behaviour of different clay-organic complexes towards polar and nonpolar liquids and pairs of immiscible or partially miscible liquids has been studied. Attempt has also been made to explain the data from X-ray examination of H-clays, their binary mixtures, and clay-organic complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The complexes, prepared according to the procedure described earlier¹, were washed free of electrolytes and other impurities with water, ethanol, and ether, pulverised to 100 mesh, and dried at 30°. The gel volumes² of the complexes in different solvents and any visible change in the nature of the mixtures were observed in the following way.

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1. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1960, 7, 27.
2. Jordan, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1949, 53, 294.

- (i) The sample of the complex (0.1 g.) was thoroughly mixed with the pure solvents or their binary mixtures (25 ml) in a well-stoppered graduated cylinder and allowed to stand undisturbed; the gel volume was recorded after 24 hr.
- (ii) In a separate set of experiments the sample (0.1 g.) was taken in each of a series of graduated cylinders and treated initially with pure solvents or mixtures of known composition. Then the percentage of either of the solvents was increased and the gel volume was recorded as above.
- (iii) For studying the behaviour of the organic clay complexes towards pairs of partially miscible or immiscible solvents, of which water was one, the solid sample (0.1 g.) was first shaken with water and again by adding an equal volume of the organic liquid and kept undisturbed for 24 hr. for attainment of equilibrium and the results were recorded. In a few cases the order was changed, i.e., organic solvent was added first and water subsequently.

The results are shown in Tables I and II and graphically represented in Fig. 1 and 2 (also Plates I-II).

Plate I

Plate II

TABLE I

*Sample.	Gel volume (ml) of the clay-organic complexes in					
	Ether.	EtOH.	Water.	CCl ₄ .	Toluene.	Acetone.
O.T.A.—aqua-gel	..	7.52	..	4.47	52.0	4.87***
„—Akli bentonite	10.53	..	2.60	..	..	7.60
P.T.A.—aqua-gel	2.45	..	2.50	..	..	1.60
C.E.-D.F. Illite	..	..	..	5.24	..	..
C.T.A.—mica	..	..	..	4.01	..	..
O.T.A.E.—M-kaolinite	..	..	..	..	..	2.16
P.T.A. „	5.09	..	3.02	..	..	..

**T—upper liquid Turbid.

*C.T.A.B.—cetyltrimethylammonium bromide.

C.E.D.A.B.—cetylthylidimethylammonium bromide.

P.T.A.I.—phenyltrimethylammonium iodide.

C.T.A. clay—cetyltrimethylammonium complex of the clay (for preparation etc. cf. Ref No, 1, 3 and 4).

TABLE II

Preferential adsorption of organic clay complexes by liquids.

Suspended material.	Nitrobenzene.	Ether.	Water + CCl ₄ .	Cyclohexane.	Amyl or butyl alcohol.
Aqua-gel (H)		W	W	..	..
F. illite (H)		W	W	..	..
B. kaolin (H)		W	W	..	..
M. clay (H)		W	W	..	..
O. T. A.-B. kaolin	W.O.	W(i ₁)	W	W(i ₁)	O
O. T. A.-aqua-gel	O,O*	O	W(i ₁)	..	..
C. T. A.-F. illite	O,O(i ₁)	i ₂	W(i ₁)	..	..
C. T. A.-M. clay	O+W,O	i ₂	W	..	..
C. T. A. Mix (R.K:AqM=1:1)	..	W+O	W+O	W+	O
C. T. A. Mix (R.K:F. I=1:1)	..	W+i ₂	..	..	..
C. T. A.-vermiculite	..	O	..	..	..
O. T. A.-mica	O	..	..	..	..
Acetyl or benzoyl. kaolinite	..	W	..	..	..
Cetyl benzonite	..	W(i ₁)	..	..	..

Note: W, O, i mean practically all the solid goes respectively to the water, organic liquid, and the interface i₂=towards water, i₁=towards organic liquid.

W(i₁)-chiefly to water-phase, a very little goes to the interface towards water.

W(i₂)- " " " " " " " " organic solvent.

*First the solid was wetted with the organic liquid and next water was added.

For abbreviation see Table I.

DISCUSSION

The sequence of wettability agrees with intake data of toluene and water³, which are a measure of the organophilic character of the complexes. The organophilic character increases in the order of increasing exchange capacity of the corresponding hydrogen systems.

It is observed that the phase to which a given organo-clay complex goes depends primarily on the liquid wetting the solid first. Thus, the kaolin complex goes to the water phase if it is first treated with water and subsequently with nitrobenzene, but it chooses the organic phase if it is first wetted with nitrobenzene. Complexes of montmorillonite and illite prefer the organic phase in either of the cases. The predominant organophilic character of aqua-gel complex is also evident from its behaviour towards different solvents of varying dielectric constants. Organophilic character of the clay complexes appears to follow the order: montmorillonite > illite > kaolinite, which is also the order of exchange capacities of the clay minerals and the order of the amounts of the organics adsorbed by the clay minerals³.

The behaviour of C.T.A.* complexes of mixtures of kaolinite and montmorillonite as well as kaolinite and illite is interesting. The individual characteristics of the component clay complexes, obtained from mixtures of clay minerals, are retained in the binary immis-

3. Chakravarti, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1957, 5, 85.

*The abbreviations used are shown in Table I

oible liquid system and may be utilised for separation of clay minerals present in a mixture⁴.

The sedimentation volumes of kaolinite and mica complexes in CCl_4 -EtOH mixtures (vide Fig. 1-2) are also suggestive of the much less pronounced organophilic character of the complexes. In contrast to this is extensive swelling of the montmorillonite complex and even in association with the kaolin complex (vide Fig. 1-2).

Fig. 1 Sedimentation volume of Clay—organic complex in CCl_4 -EtOH.

The sedimentation volumes of binary mixtures do not show additivity. If the montmorillonite complex is first wetted with CCl_4 and then an increasing amount of ethanol is added to the mixture, disregarding the little change in concentration of the solid, the curve assumes the form as depicted in curve 3, Fig. 1. If instead of CCl_4 , it is first treated with solvating mixtures containing different amounts of ethanol, the curves (2 & 3, Fig. 1) exhibit a different course.

The graphs of *Fithian illite and *Mohitnagar soil clay are more or less similar in features to each other, but differ from the other clay minerals. Instead of one maximum, as obtained in montmorillonite, mica, and binary mixtures of kaolinite and montmorillonite (cf. graphs 6 to 8 and 13, Fig. 1&2) and two maxima of montmorillonite, where the experimental conditions are slightly changed, three maxima are obtained when the complexes are first wetted with CCl_4 and the percentage of ethanol is increased by subsequent additions (curves 10,11,12, Fig. 2).

The features of the curve for aque-gel complex are similar to those obtained by Jordan⁵, using ethanol-toluene or ester-toluene mixtures. According to Jordan, solvation of montmorillonite complexes depends on (i) the extent of the surface coating of the clay

*Abbreviated as F and M in the tables.

⁴ Chakravarti, D. Phil. thesis, University of Calcutta, 1959.

particles by organic substances, (ii) the degree of saturation of the b.e.c. of the clay by the organic cations, and (iii) the nature of the solvating liquid. For the same clay complex, the degree of solvation will principally depend on (iii). The process of penetration of a liquid for a partially saturated complex will depend on the adsorption energy of the liquid for the uncoated clay as well as the organic coating itself. Both the conditions are fulfilled by a single liquid like nitrobenzene or by a binary liquid mixture of the type CCl_4 -EtOH (cf. Table II). The adsorption of the polar ethanol molecules by the clay tends to break the aggregates and thus exposes the organic coating to the organophilic liquid. The initial rise of swelling and sedimentation volume may be explained in this way. A maximum sedimentation volume at an optimum concentration of ethanol is therefore likely. The positions of the maxima for different clay minerals are seen to be different. At very high concentrations of ethanol, the organic complex deflocculates, reducing thereby the sedimentation volume.

Fig. 2. Sedimentation volume of clays organic complex in CCl_4 -EtOH.

- | | |
|-----------------------------|------------------------------|
| 6. C. E. D. AqM (1%). | 10. O. T. A. M. clay (0.4%). |
| 7. O. T. A. Mx. XVIII (1%). | 11. C. E. D. illite (0.4%). |
| 8. " " XVII (1.1%). | 12. " " (0.64%). |
| 9. C. E. D. kaolin (1%). | 13. O. T. A. mica (1.0%). |
| | 14. C. E. D. R. K. ("). |
| | 10-12. Total vol. = 25 ml. |
| | 13-14. " " 10 " |

Total vol. = 10 ml.

Nonpolar CCl_4 hardly wets the clay particles, but can only penetrate into the capillaries, causing a little swelling. But when a mixture of EtOH and CCl_4 is added to the organic clay, the former, owing to its high polarity, is taken up both in the capillary space and between the lattice layers. In the latter, the polar molecules become somewhat oriented around the organic groups already present and also on the uncoated portions of the surface. The mixture assumes a gel-like appearance. The volume, as shown in Fig. 2, corresponding to 2% EtOH, is, strictly speaking, not the sedimentation volume but the volume of the gel. The tendency of the clay-organic complexes to form gels in any solvent of highly polar and organophilic character (nitrobenzene) or any binary mixture of polar and nonpolar solvents ($\text{EtOH} + \text{CCl}_4$) may be traced to the micellar theory or organic jellies,

proposed by Frankenheim and Nageli⁶, or, to the network or sponge-like structure of inorganic jellies. The clay micelles, similar to the molecular aggregates, take up the polar liquid (and also nonpolar but organophilic CCl_4) in such a manner that these are surrounded by a layer of the polar liquid, the thickness of which is determined by the relative intensity of attraction of the solvent molecules for the organo-clay complex and for each other. Corresponding to about 10%, 11%, 22.5% of EtOH (cf. curves 1-3, Fig. 1), flocculation of the gel takes place at a particular concentration of the polar solvent in the solvating mixture.

The position of the maximum flocculation region is found to be dependent on the nature of the primary wetting agent. The increase in sedimentation volume at this stage suggests that the adsorption of sufficient ethanol by the clay complex makes the flakes more accessible to CCl_4 , a few molecules of which may penetrate the interlaminal space. A large number of CCl_4 molecules may also be entrained between the solid particles, causing an increase in the effective volume of the system. But the degree of solvation of the clay complexes, first wetted by CCl_4 , is found to be less than that of the complexes when wetted first with EtOH- CCl_4 mixture. The exclusion of CCl_4 from the capillary pores is supposed to be effected slowly and may not be complete till at higher concentrations of the polar solvent; as a result, the increase in sedimentation volume is also restricted. In all the above cases, the sedimentation volume is seen to be diminished after the maxima, probably due to the dispersive action of the solvent (*vide supra*). The explanation of the first two maxima, as noticed in illite or lillite soil clay, is similar to those of montmorillonite, but in these cases an increase in sedimentation volume (strictly speaking, gel volume) occurs at higher concentrations of ethanol. This may be attributed to the low dispersibility of the said complex in EtOH, in contrast to the respective high and very low dispersibility of montmorillonite and kaolinite complexes. It should be pointed out that presence of water in ethanol is likely to affect the experiment. Fresh ethanol, distilled over lime and subsequently kept in contact with sodium wires, was used for the experiments reported in Fig. 2A. In all other cases ethanol over lime alone was used.

Mixture of Clays.—The X-ray data (Table III) of a binary mixture of aqua-gel and *Rajmahal kaolin show that the characteristics of both montmorillonite and kaolinite, which are respectively the only clay minerals present in these samples, are maintained in the mixture.

Soil Clay.—The data (Table III) obtained with the soil clay indicate the presence of illite as the predominant mineral with a very small amount of kaolinite.

C. T. A. B. Clay.—The data of the C. T. A. * Rajmahal kaolin are similar to those of the hydrogen clay treated with glycerol. Thus the introduction of organic ions in the exchange sites little affects the X-ray data when compared with the values obtained by treatment of the hydrogen clay with glycerol.

C. T. A. Aqua-gel.—Unlike kaolinite, montmorillonite shows variations in the X-ray reflections after introduction of large organic cations in the exchange sites. The very

6. Weiser, "Colloid Chemistry", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., London, 1947.

*Abbreviated as B in the tables.

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strong and broad band corresponds to 22.33 to 15.99 KX X-ray reflections. The shifting of the reflections towards higher values suggests the expansion of the c-axis spacing.

TABLE III

X-ray examination of H-clays, their binary mixtures, and clay-organic complexes.

Aqua-gel (H) (AqM)+ glycerol.			Bajmahal kaolin (H) (B.K.)+ glycerol.		Mixture (B.K. AqM=1:1).			Mohitanagar clay(H).		
d.	I.		d.	I.	d.	I.	Sh.	d.	I.	
17.6	vs		7.0	vs	17.56	vs	br.	10.04	w	
					14.66					
8.9	m		4.4	s	7.02	s		6.97	vw	
4.4	s		4.2	s				4.35	m	
					4.30	s	br.	3.58	m	
					4.20			3.95	vw	
								2.99	m	
					3.43	m				
					3.22	vw				
O.T.A. Bajmahal kaolin (without glycerol treatment).				O.T.A. aqua-gel.			O.T.A. vermiculite			
d.	I.	Sh.		d.	I.	Sh.	d.	I.	Sh.	
7.02	s			22.33	vs	v.br.	24.54	vs	v.br.	
				15.99						
4.12				10.26	vw		17.50		br.	
							14.66			
3.45	ms			4.47	s	br.				
2.44	ms			4.35						
				3.61	m		2.60	m		
2.22	ms			3.26	w		2.33	vw		
				3.02	w					
				2.51	m	br.				

Note: d = interplanar spacings in KX units.
 I = the order of relative intensities.
 Sh = shape of the band; s = strong; v.s. = very strong; w = weak; v.w. = very weak;
 v.br = very broad; br = broad; m = moderate.

Assuming 9.6 Å as the basal plane spacing of montmorillonite laminae¹, the expansion in the c-axis dimension corresponds to 12 Å, which is approximately three times the van der Waals diameter of a methyl group.⁷

The above results strongly suggest the formation of three layers of the organic ion between the basal plane lattices of the montmorillonite. The number of layers is a gain found to be approximately equal to the next higher integral values of the number of equivalents of the organic groups per exchange position of montmorillonite^{1,3}. This, in all probability, necessitates the formation of multiple layers of the long-chain organic cations or molecules as the surface area per exchange position may not accommodate them in a single layer. Approximate surface area of montmorillonite is 169 Å²; diameter of Me group being 4 Å⁷.

7. Grim, "Clay Mineralogy", Mc. Graw Hill Book Co. Inc., 1963.

Another feature of the analysis of montmorillonite and vermiculite complexes is exhibited by the X-ray scattering close to the primary beam showing high-spacing bands. This, termed as central scattering, has been discussed earlier⁴.

C. T. A. Vermiculite.—Barahed⁸ and Sinha (née Sengupta⁹) observed that in addition to the 14.63 KX line for the raw and Mg⁺⁺-saturated vermiculite and H-vermiculite, all the samples either in the form of raw powder (without glycerol treatment), single crystal (with or without glycerol treatment), and Mg-clay (glycerol treated) show a strong basal reflection corresponding to 24.46 KX. Sinha⁹ and Adhikari¹⁰ also observed the 17.7 KX spacing characteristic of montmorillonite in the case of glycerolated H-vermiculite and glycerolated H-clays and Mg-clays-respectively.

The diffraction data of C.T.A. derivative of vermiculite, as recorded in Table III, exhibit differences with H-vermiculite. The periphery away from the centre of the strong band corresponds to 24.54 KX spacing. The uniform intensity of the band extended up to the central spot, or the primary beam suggests that greater spacings are also present in this region, which perhaps arise out of the interlamellar adsorption of a large number of C. T. A. groups between the unit cells of the mineral. A wide range of particle sizes may be present. In addition, a second band is noticed corresponding to 17.5-14.66 KX spacing, in place of two lines at 14.63 and 17.70 KX units, characteristic of H⁺ or Mg⁺⁺ saturated vermiculite respectively.

From the above data the formation of multilayers of organic molecules in the basal planes of vermiculite may be visualised. The amount of adsorption in vermiculite as, calculated from %carbon as well as the intake of toluene by the complexes, partly supports this point.

Incidentally, the organo-clay derivatives have been used for the purpose of separation of the component clay minerals from their mixture. A suitable combination of properties, e.g. of charge reversal and development of organophilic character, as discussed above, seems to be the answer to a satisfactory separation of the ingredient clay minerals of a mixture.

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8. *Am. Min.*, 1948, **31**, 635.

9. D. Phil thesis, University of Calcutta, 1959.

10. Adhikari, *this Journal*, 1958, **21**, 149.

11. Chakravarti, *Science & Culture*, 1958, **22**, 170.